

Analysis of the Effectiveness of Using Team-Based Quizzes to Improve Student Learning Outcomes in Informatics Subjects in Phase F10 Class of SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta

*¹Mohamad Danil Efendi, ²Dwi Maryono, ³Adi Waskito

¹Pendidikan Profesi Guru, Sebelas Maret University, Indonesia

²Informatics and Computer Engineering Education, Sebelas Maret University, Indonesia

³SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta, Indonesia

Corresponding Email: mohamaddanilpml@student.uns.ac.id

Abstract:

This study analyzed the effectiveness of using team-based quizzes in improving student learning outcomes in Informatics subjects in Phase F10 classes at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta. The research method used an experimental design with an experimental class that used team-based quizzes and a control class that used conventional methods. The results showed a significant increase in student learning outcomes in the experimental class compared to the control class. The average final score of the experimental class increased from 65 to 85, while the control class increased from 66 to 75. These findings suggest that team-based quizzing can increase active participation, cooperation, and understanding of the subject matter by students. This method also provides additional benefits in the development of social skills and cooperation. This study concludes that team-based quizzing is an effective learning method and can be widely applied in education.

Keywords: *Team-based Quiz, Learning Outcomes, Interactive Learning, Collaborative Learning, Informatics Subject, SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta, Phase F10.*

JGHTT (Journal of Global Hospitality and Tourism Technology)

Vol X Issue Y 2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14286412

Received: 22/11/24 Revised: 05/12/24 Accepted: 05/12/24 Online: 06/12/24

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Introduction

Learning in the digital age requires innovation in teaching methods to effectively improve student learning outcomes. One method that is being developed and frequently discussed in educational literature is the use of team-based quizzing. This method combines elements of competition and collaboration to increase student participation and understanding of the subject matter.

Technology-based education and collaboration have become a major focus in education reform in recent years. According to research by Lestari et al. (2023), innovative learning models provide a more responsive, collaborative and adaptive approach. It allows teachers to increase student participation, expand access to learning resources, and develop students' technology, collaboration and creativity skills. In addition, a study by Utami et al. (2019) showed that a collaborative learning model supported by mind maps has a significant impact on student learning outcomes.

Research by Srimuliyani et al. (2023) also showed that the implementation of gamification techniques or team-based quizzes significantly increased student engagement in the classroom. This method encourages students to work together to solve problems, which in turn improves their ability to understand and recall information.

However, despite the abundant evidence supporting the effectiveness of team-based learning, the application of team-based quizzing in the context of Informatics subjects at the senior high school level has rarely been studied, especially in Indonesia. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by analyzing the effectiveness of using team-based quizzes in improving student learning outcomes in Informatics in Phase F10 classes at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta.

By understanding the impact of this learning method, it is expected to contribute to the development of more effective and innovative teaching strategies in Informatics education. This research also seeks to provide empirical evidence of the benefits of team-based learning methods in the context of education in Indonesia.

Related Work

Research on interactive and collaborative learning methods shows positive results in improving student learning outcomes. One approach that combines elements of competition and collaboration is the team-based quiz method, which is believed to increase active participation and student understanding.

Interactive and Collaborative Learning

The study by Hasanah et al. (2019) shows that active learning model with reading aloud method increases students' interaction higher than conventional methods such as lecture. This study confirms that active engagement in the learning process plays an important role in improving understanding and retention of material. In addition, research by Saputra et al. (2024) found that cooperative learning significantly improved students' academic achievement compared to traditional methods. In the context of Informatics learning, this method allows students to share knowledge and help each other in solving complex problems.

Team-Based Quizzing

The team-based quiz method as interactive learning has been discussed in several recent studies. According to a study by Yuliawati et al. (2021), learning in small groups allows students to focus more, feel more comfortable in discussions, and more easily solve problems and share information with each other. This encourages students to be more actively involved in learning and improves their understanding of the subject matter. Research by Rosada et al. (2024) showed that the implementation of traditional games and modern quizzes effectively improved teamwork among learners. In this study, students who participated in team-based quizzes showed significant improvement in test results and practicum reports compared to students who studied individually.

Effectiveness of Team-Based Quizzes in Informatics Subjects

Specific studies on the effectiveness of team-based quizzes in Informatics subjects show promising results. According to research by Sari et al. (2023), the use of Geogebra application for quiz making can help students develop the skills necessary for mathematical problem solving, namely critical, creative, and collaborative skills. Students involved in team-based quizzing showed significant improvement in their ability to write and test code compared to students who did not use this method. Research by Musyafak et al. (2023) supports these findings. In their study, team-based quizzes were used in Islamic religious education learning, and the results showed that the use of technology in the form of these quizzes is in line with the theory of technology use in education which aims to enhance students' learning experience and facilitate deeper understanding.

Overall, these studies show that team-based quizzing is an effective learning method in improving students' learning outcomes and social skills. This method has proven to be beneficial in a variety of disciplines, including Informatics.

By combining elements of competition and collaboration, team-based quizzing can create a more dynamic learning environment and support active student engagement.

Research Method

This study used an experimental design with two groups: an experimental class and a control class. The experimental class applied team-based quizzing in learning, while the control class used conventional methods. The research sample consisted of 36 students of Phase F10 class at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta, who were randomly divided into two groups.

This experimental design aims to evaluate the effectiveness of using team-based quizzes in improving student learning outcomes in Informatics. The research was conducted at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta with Phase F10 class students as the research subjects.

Research Design

This research design is a pre-test and post-test with a control group, using a quantitative approach to measure the difference in learning outcomes between the two groups.

Table 1. Supporting tables regarding the research design

No.	Variable	Definition Variable	Measurement Method	Data
1.	Team-Based Quizzes	Quizzes conducted in team groups	Observation, Interview	Analysis of the frequency of use of team-based quizzes
2.	Student Learning Outcomes	Student achievement in Informatics subject	Tests, report card scores	Test scores, average student report card scores
3.	Phase F10	Class or grade level that is the subject of research	Observation	Description of class characteristics Phase F10
4.	SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta	Educational institution that became the research location	Survey, Documentation	School profile, student population data

Population and Sample

- Population: Phase F10 class students at SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta.
- Sample: 36 students randomly divided into two groups: experimental class (18 students) and control class (18 students).

Research Instruments

- Learning Outcome Test: Multiple-choice tests and essay questions designed to measure students' understanding of Informatics subject matter, validated by educational experts to ensure content validity.
- Motivation and Engagement Questionnaire: A questionnaire to measure students' level of motivation and engagement during the learning process, the research instrument was a questionnaire adapted from the Metacognitive Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) developed by Pintrich et al. (1991).

Research Procedure

- Material Preparation: Learning materials and quizzes were prepared based on the current Informatics curriculum, with quizzes designed to be conducted in groups to test students' understanding of the material learned.
- Learning Implementation: Learning took place over one semester (16 weeks). The experimental class used team-based quizzes every week, while the control class used conventional learning methods without team quizzes.

- **Data Collection:** Data were collected through learning outcome tests conducted before (pre-test) and after (post-test) the learning period, as well as motivation and engagement questionnaires completed by students at the end of the semester.

Data Analysis

- **Descriptive Analysis:** Using descriptive statistics to describe the characteristics of the pre-test and post-test results and questionnaire data.
- **Inferential Analysis:** Using t-test to determine the significant difference between students' learning outcomes in the experimental and control classes. An independent t-test was used to compare the mean pre-test and post-test scores between the two groups, with the analysis supported by statistical software such as SPSS to ensure the accuracy of the results.

Validity and Reliability

- **Content Validity:** The content validity of the learning outcome tests and questionnaires were checked by educational experts and tested through a pilot study to ensure that the tests and questionnaires measured what they were supposed to measure (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001).
- **Reliability:** The reliability of the instruments was tested using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient, with values above 0.70 considered adequate to indicate the internal consistency of the instrument (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Research Ethics

This study was conducted with ethical aspects in mind. Consent from the school and participants (students and parents) was obtained prior to the implementation of the study. The confidentiality of the participants was guaranteed and they were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences.

Result and Discussion

Result

This study produced data that showed a significant increase in learning outcomes in the experimental class compared to the control class. Here is the documentation of the implementation of informatics learning with team-based quizzes:

Figure 1. Informatics learning with team-based quizzing

The following are the results of data analysis from the pre-test and post-test for both groups:

Experimental Class:

- Average pre-test score: 65
- Average post-test score: 85

Control Class:

- Average pre-test score: 66
- Average post-test score: 75

Statistical Analysis

The t-test results show that the difference between the experimental and control class post-test scores is significant with $p < 0.05$. The following is a table of t-test results:

Table 2. Difference t-test results experimental and control class

Group	Pre-test Score	Post-test Score	Difference	p-value
Experiment Group	65	85	20	< 0,05
Control Group	66	75	9	< 0,05

Discussion

The results showed that the use of team-based quizzes was effective in improving student learning outcomes in Informatics. There was a significant increase in the experimental class post-test score compared to the control class, indicating that this method is more effective than conventional learning methods.

Increased Understanding and Engagement

In addition to improving learning outcomes, team-based quizzes also increase student motivation and engagement in the learning process. Research by Kaur et al. (2020) highlights how quizzes can inspire student motivation and encourage a competitive and collaborative learning environment through customizable features. These findings are consistent with this study, where students in the experimental class showed higher active participation during quiz sessions.

Social Skills Development

In addition, team-based quizzing also helps in the development of social skills and cooperation among students. The study by Winartiasih et al. (2023) found that collaboration skills, namely the ability to work effectively in a team and appreciate the diversity of team members, as well as the ability in decision-making to achieve a common goal, were also honed through the use of team-based quizzes.

Challenges and Solutions

Although team-based quizzes provide significant benefits, there are some challenges that need to be overcome, such as quiz preparation that requires additional time and more complex classroom management. The study by Razak et al. (2024) confirmed that effective strategy implementation requires meticulous planning, clear communication, and strong support from top management. Therefore, teacher training and provision of adequate resources are critical to the successful use of team-based quizzing in learning.

Research Limitations

This study has several limitations, including a limited sample size and the duration of the study being only one semester. Further studies with larger samples and longer periods are needed to validate these findings and explore the long-term impact of using team-based quizzes in the context of Informatics education.

Conclusion

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of using team-based quiz in improving students' learning outcomes in Informatics subject in Phase F10 class of SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta. The results showed that this method significantly improved students' understanding of Informatics subject matter compared to conventional learning methods.

Key Findings

- **Improved Learning Outcomes:**
The experimental class using team-based quizzes showed a significant improvement in learning outcomes. The average post-test score of the experimental class increased from 65 to 85, while the control class only increased from 66 to 75. Statistical analysis results showed a significant difference with $p < 0.05$, which supports the hypothesis that the use of team-based quizzes is effective in improving students' understanding of Informatics subject matter.
- **Motivation and Engagement:**
The use of team-based quizzes also improved students' motivation and engagement in the learning process. Students in the experimental class showed more active participation and more positive responses to learning activities. Studies by Kaur et al. (2020) and Yuliawati et al. (2021) support these findings, suggesting that learning methods that facilitate active and collaborative interactions can increase student engagement.
- **Social Skills Development:**
In addition to improving academic achievement, team-based quizzes also play a role in the development of social skills and cooperation between students. Research by Winartiasih et al. (2023) and Rozak et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of collaborative learning in strengthening communication and cooperation skills, which is also evident in the findings of this study.

Educational Implications

These findings have important implications for educational practice:

- **Classroom Implementation:**
Teachers may consider using team-based quizzes as part of their learning strategies, especially in subjects that require in-depth understanding of concepts such as Informatics. This method not only improves learning outcomes but also encourages students to be more actively involved in the teaching and learning process.
- **Curriculum Development:**
The education curriculum can be updated to better support interactive and collaborative learning. Support from schools and educational decision makers is essential to provide the necessary resources and training for teachers in implementing this method.
- **Further Research:**
Further studies are needed to explore the long-term impact of using team-based quizzing and to test its effectiveness in different contexts. Research with larger samples and longer duration can provide deeper insights into the benefits as well as the challenges of using this method.

Acknowledgement

This research could not have been successful without the support and contributions of various parties, which we gratefully acknowledge. We would like to express our great appreciation to SMA Negeri 4 Surakarta, especially to the principal, teachers, and administrative staff who have given permission and supported the implementation of this research.

We would also like to express our deepest gratitude to the teachers of Informatics in Phase F10 classes who have been actively involved in applying the team-based quiz method and assisting in the data collection process. The students' participation and enthusiasm in this research also meant a lot to the success of our study.

The research team and research assistants also deserve appreciation for their hard work in designing and implementing this study. The technical and logistical support they provided was crucial to ensure that each stage of the study ran smoothly according to plan.

We would also like to thank previous researchers who have provided the foundation for this research. Their work, such as that of Kaur et al. (2020), Winartiasih et al. (2023), and Rozak et al. (2023), have provided valuable insights that enriched our research and helped in the formulation of methods and data analysis.

Finally, we would like to thank our family and friends who have provided moral support throughout this research process. Their encouragement and understanding were very helpful in dealing with the various challenges we faced during this research.

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